

ADAPTATION OF GRADUATES OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS TO PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITIES

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Graduates of higher education institutions are not well versed in teaching methodology and techniques, they are incapable of solving problems of pure education and are not able to establish strong ties with the families of students. The formation of practical knowledge in educators requires a slightly longer period. Graduates of higher education institutions are not considered fully specialists. Taking this into account, the university must combine the complex process of the professional formation of the future teacher (professional orientation, adaptation, professional choice, dynamics of the professional formation of the future teacher). The problem of adapting a young teacher is considered to be a complex and multi-factor process. It is a special object of management inside and outside the educational institution, the effectiveness of which depends on the completeness of knowledge about the essence and mechanisms. The management of adaptation processes is mainly related to the fields of pedagogy, social psychology and sociology.

Currently, the requirements for the consciousness of a modern employee are changing. He must have a significant flexibility of consciousness, a wide range of thinking and a systematic nature, psychologically prepared for changes in the nature of working conditions and labor activity, which are associated with replenishment and renewal of his knowledge. This principle means that a young pedagogical employee must develop a desire to constantly improve and replenish his knowledge and the ability to master them [1].

In the educational system of New Uzbekistan, the role of intellectual education in the scientific field is important and it has several features:

- Education of students to meet the requirements of scientific, technical and social development;
- Forming the foundations of a scientific outlook;
- Development of mental powers and knowledge of students;
- Developing the need for education, constantly replenishing their knowledge, expanding the general outlook;

In turn, the pedagogical employee must raise his enthusiasm for his field before carrying out the above tasks, take a creative approach, be aware of the latest achievements in his field and related fields, know the relevant literature.

There are several reasons for a decrease in the adaptive potential of young professionals at the stage of entering the profession. We can cite the following factors that hinder successful psychological adaptation.

- Inadequate professional training;
- Insufficient motivation for professional growth;
- Lack of support for young professionals by the administration
- Underdevelopment of professionally important qualities in a person, etc [2].

The process of professional adaptation of young educators is a controlled process and there are factors for its success:

- Motivational expectations of a young educator, professional training as an educator;
- Theoretical justification of the essence, role and significance of professional adaptation to increase the effectiveness of pedagogical formation of a young educator;
- Creating conditions for the development of professional and socio-psychological adaptation of young educators in educational institutions;
- Improving the feature of combining theory with practice, providing for holistic professional thinking and the formation of specific pedagogical skills in students;
- Development of targeted programs for improving the interaction of the University and the school when working with young educators;
- Formation by public education authorities of organizational measures to increase the adaptation capabilities of young teachers;
- Creating permanent conditions for the professional self-improvement of a young teachers;
- Implementation of the pedagogical leadership system for professional adaptation of young teachers [3].

The adaptation of a young specialist is not only an adaptation to new conditions of life, but also an active assimilation of the norms of professional communication, labor discipline, production skills, traditions of the labor team, that is, the process of entering a new social environment for him [4].

Professional adaptation is carried out on two levels:

- a) External

b) Internal

Externally, a person adapts to the social environment, perceives life norms and values, while making adjustments to relations with society.

At the internal level of personality, a process of self-adaptation occurs, as a result of which there is a desire for self-confidence and behavior, a process of changing beliefs, reassessment of values, self-development.

This allows young workers to distinguish between external and internal factors of adaptation to professional activities in an educational institution.

External factors include:

- a) Relationship with students;
- b) Relationship with the pedagogical community;
- c) Distinctive features of the educational institution;
- d) Distinctive features of the work of young workers;
- e) The need for creative work;
- f) Psychological atmosphere;

Internal factors include:

- a) Interest in the profession;
- b) Motivation;
- c) Desire for self-realization;
- d) Mutual assistance;
- e) Creativity;
- f) Self-development;
- g) Self-education;
- h) Responsibility;
- i) Self-criticism;
- j) Reflection of one's own behavior [5].

In educational institutions, the adaptation of young educators to professional activities is a complex and long-lasting process. This period includes the formation of professional knowledge, skills, important qualities necessary for further development purpose. The period of professional adaptation is the necessary stage, which is a prerequisite for the professional formation and development of a specialist.

References:

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